

SPECTROSCOPIC AND QUANTUM CHEMICAL ANALYSIS ON THE STRUCTURE OF TELMISARTAN

B Latha¹, S Gunasekaran² and G R Ramkumaar³

¹*Department of Physics, Dr. M.G.R. Educational & Research Institute University,
Chennai 600095, TN, India.*

²*Research and Development, St. Peter's Institute of Higher Education and Research,
Avadi, Chennai 600054, TN, India.*

³*Department of Physics, C. Kandaswami Naidu College for Men,
Anna Nagar East, Chennai 600102, TN, India.*

Abstract

Telmisartan is an angiotensin II receptor blocker used in the therapy of hypertension. The spectral properties of Telmisartan were investigated using FTIR, FT-Raman techniques. The structure of the molecule was optimized and structural properties were determined using Quantum chemical methods using B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) and B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) as basis sets. The theoretical wavenumbers are compared with experimental FTIR and FT-Raman spectra. The electronic properties were also calculated and interpreted using UV-Vis and HOMO-LUMO analysis.

Keywords: Telmisartan, FTIR, Quantum Chemical Computation, Homo-Lumo, FTIR, FT Raman.

1. INTRODUCTION

Medicines form an indispensable component of health systems in the prevention, diagnosis and treatment of disease. The element that makes the drug work potentially is the active pharmaceutical ingredient. It affects the physiological functioning of a body. Each drug can be classified into one or more drug classes. The compound chosen for the present investigation is Telmisartan. It is an angiotensin II receptor antagonist (ARB) used in the management of high blood pressure. The study of structural activity relationships of existing drugs supported with computational methods enhances the better understanding of molecular properties and thus greatly improves its therapeutic values [1].

It has the extended half-life of any ARB (24 hours) [2] and the largest volume of distribution among ARBs [3,4]. It is chemically described as 2-(4-([4-Methyl-6-(1-methyl-1H-1,3-benzodiazol-2-yl)-2-propyl-1H-1,3-benzodiazol-1-yl]methyl)phenyl)benzoic acid. Its empirical formula is C₃₃H₃₀N₄O₂. Its molecular weight is 514.63 gm/mol. It is a white to slightly yellowish solid. It is insoluble in water and soluble in strong base. This belongs to the class of organic compounds known as biphenyls and derivatives. These are organic compounds containing two benzene rings linked together by a C-C bond. Thus, an attempt was undertaken to combine the quantum chemical computational methods with versatile spectroscopic techniques to reprofile the stability affirmation of chosen drug molecule.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The pure sample of Telmisartan was obtained from Sigma Aldrich Chemical Company, USA with a stated purity of 98% and used as such for investigation purposes. The FTIR spectrum has been recorded in the region $4000\text{--}400\text{cm}^{-1}$ using KBr pellet technique with 4cm^{-1} resolution on PERKIN ELMER FTIR spectrometer at SAIF, IIT Madras, India.

3. QUANTUM CHEMICAL COMPUTATIONAL METHODS

The quantum chemical computational methods are an important tool in the characterization of larger molecular systems by computing schrodingerequations [5]. These methods are employed to get characteristic quality of information on the molecular structure. The use of density functional theory for studying the properties of various biomolecules has been reported by several studies [6], ground state energy and other molecular properties [7,8]. In the present work, quantum chemical computational methods like Density Functional B3LYP method with the 6-31G(d,p) and 6-311G(d,p) basis sets are employed to study the complete vibrational spectra of the entitled compound. The structure of Telmisartan was optimized to derive molecular properties. These calculations were performed using the Gaussian 03W package program with gauss view molecular visualization [9,10].

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Molecular Geometry

Molecular geometry is a three-dimensional arrangement of atoms which describe the shape of a molecule. The optimal geometry is determined by the values of coordinates for which the total energy is minimum. It governs the properties and the interaction of drug molecules with their receptors. The optimized molecular structure of the isolated Telmisartan molecule is calculated using B3LYP method with the 6-31G(d,p) and 6-311G(d,p) basis sets. The comparative optimized geometrical parameters are listed in **Table.1**. **Fig 1:** shows the optimized structure of Telmisartan (atom numbering scheme adopted in the study). The bond lengths are compared with the literature values [11].

Fig 1: Atomic numbering scheme of Telmisartan

The bond length can be determined by the number of bonded electrons. The higher the bond order, the stronger the pull between the two atoms and shorter the bond length. As more number of electron participation increases in the bond formation, the bond is shorter [12].

Table 1: Literature values and theoretical optimized geometric parameters of Telmisartan by B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) and B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) methods

Bond length (Å)	Literature value	6-31G(d,p)	6-311G(d,p)	Bond length (Å)	Literature value	6-31G(d,p)	6-311G(d,p)
C ₁ -C ₂	1.523	1.505	1.505	C ₂₁ -C ₂₅	1.39	1.395	1.393
C ₁ -O ₈	1.43	1.207	1.199	C ₂₂ -C ₂₃	1.39	1.391	1.388
C ₁ -O ₉	1.43	1.362	1.361	C ₂₂ -C ₃₉	1.523	1.505	1.504
C ₂ -C ₃	1.39	1.415	1.412	C ₂₃ -C ₂₄	1.39	1.418	1.416
C ₂ -C ₇	1.39	1.405	1.402	C ₂₃ -H ₅₁	1.09	1.085	1.083
C ₃ -C ₄	1.39	1.406	1.403	C ₂₄ -C ₂₅	1.39	1.402	1.399
C ₃ -C ₁₀	1.523	1.493	1.493	C ₂₄ -C ₃₀	1.44	1.472	1.471
C ₄ -C ₅	1.39	1.393	1.391	C ₂₅ -H ₅₂	1.09	1.085	1.082
C ₄ -H ₄₀	1.09	1.086	1.084	C ₂₆ -C ₂₇	1.523	1.533	1.532
C ₅ -C ₆	1.39	1.394	1.391	C ₂₆ -H ₅₃	1.09	1.099	1.097
C ₅ -H ₄₁	1.11	1.086	1.084	C ₂₆ -H ₅₄	1.09	1.101	1.099
C ₆ -C ₇	1.39	1.392	1.390	C ₂₇ -C ₂₈	1.523	1.530	1.530
C ₆ -H ₄₂	1.09	1.085	1.084	C ₂₇ -H ₅₅	1.09	1.095	1.093
C ₇ -H ₄₃	1.09	1.087	1.085	C ₂₇ -H ₅₆	1.09	1.095	1.093
O ₉ -H ₄₄	0.98	0.968	0.965	C ₂₈ -H ₅₇	1.09	1.094	1.093
C ₁₀ -C ₁₁	1.39	1.403	1.402	C ₂₈ -H ₅₈	1.09	1.096	1.095
C ₁₀ -C ₁₅	1.39	1.405	1.400	C ₂₈ -H ₅₉	1.09	1.096	1.095
C ₁₁ -C ₁₂	1.39	1.393	1.389	N ₂₉ -C ₃₀	1.37	1.395	1.393
C ₁₁ -H ₄₅	1.09	1.082	1.080	N ₂₉ -C ₃₃	1.37	1.386	1.385
C ₁₂ -C ₁₃	1.39	1.399	1.398	N ₂₉ -C ₃₈	1.37	1.453	1.454
C ₁₂ -H ₄₆	1.09	1.088	1.086	C ₃₀ -N ₃₁	1.37	1.319	1.316
Bond angle (°)	Literature value	6-31G(d,p)	6-311G(d,p)	Bond angle (°)	Literature value	6-31G(d,p)	6-311G(d,p)
C ₂ -C ₁ -O ₈	122.9	125.7	125.5	C ₁₃ -C ₁₆ -H ₄₉	109.4	109.6	109.5
C ₂ -C ₁ -O ₉	109.5	114.6	114.6	C ₁₃ -C ₁₆ -H ₅₀	109.4	110.1	109.4
O ₈ -C ₁ -O ₉	122.9	119.6	119.9	N ₁₇ -C ₁₆ -H ₄₉	109.46	108.8	108.2
C ₁ -C ₂ -C ₃	120	123.3	123.1	N ₁₇ -C ₁₆ -H ₅₀	109.46	107.0	107.7
C ₄ -C ₅ -C ₆	120	119.9	119.9	N ₁₉ -C ₂₀ -C ₂₁	118	110.3	110.2
C ₅ -C ₆ -C ₇	120	119.2	119.3	N ₁₇ -C ₂₁ -C ₂₀	118	105.0	105.0
C ₅ -C ₆ -H ₄₂	120	120.7	120.7	N ₁₇ -C ₂₁ -C ₂₅	118	132.3	132.2
C ₇ -C ₆ -H ₄₂	120	120.1	120.1	C ₂₀ -C ₂₁ -C ₂₅	120	122.7	122.8
C ₆ -C ₇ -H ₄₃	120	119.6	119.5	C ₂₃ -C ₂₂ -C ₃₉	120	122.6	122.6
C ₁ -O ₉ -H ₄₄	109	109.5	109.6	C ₂₂ -C ₂₃ -C ₂₄	120	122.8	122.9
C ₃ -C ₁₀ -C ₁₁	120	122.7	122.6	N ₂₉ -C ₃₃ -C ₃₂	105.3	105.3	105.3
C ₃ -C ₁₀ -C ₁₅	120	119.0	119.2	C ₂₄ -C ₂₃ -H ₅₁	120	117.4	117.3
C ₁₁ -C ₁₀ -C ₁₅	120	118.2	118.2	C ₂₃ -C ₂₄ -C ₂₅	120	120.4	120.4

For the entitled compound under study, the bond length between N₂₉-C₃₈ was found to be 1.45 Å by both methods which is due to the presence of hydrogen atoms at that position which is almost close to the bond length of 1.48 Å in an isolated C-N single bond.

The calculated C-N distances are similar to the values to the values reported by MMZaho et al [13]. The aromatic carbon-carbon bond lengths are well within the range $1.39\text{\AA} - 1.402\text{\AA}$ by both methods. It is clear that the bond length between C_1-C_2 , $C_{13}-C_{16}$, $C_{22}-C_{39}$, $C_{27}-C_{28}$ are identical and their distances are in the range $1.50\text{\AA} - 1.53\text{\AA}$ shows single bond character.

This increase in the bond length when compared to other carbon atoms is due to the hydrogen involvement in intermolecular interactions. Moreover, these bonds are found to be weakest bonds as their bond lengths are greater. The strongest bonds are observed between $O_9-H_{44} = 0.96\text{\AA}$ by using 6-311G(d, p) basis set. This is because of the bonds which includes hydrogen can be quite short. The more tightly held the bond will be, the more dominant the character.

The angle that is formed between the two adjacent bonds on the same atom is a bond angle. The unit of bond angle is either degree or minute or second. The shape of a particular molecule is determined by the specific arrangement of atoms in it and the bond angles. Therefore, bond angle determines the shape of a molecule. The bond angle between $N_{17}-C_{21}-C_{20}$, $N_{29}-C_{33}-C_{32}$ was found to be 105.3° by both methods which would increase the 'P' character of the orbital. The decrease in the bond angle is due to the electronegativity character of nitrogen atoms [11].

The geometries of SP_2 hybridised carbon atoms are trigonal which has bond angle 120° . The C-H bonds are equal because they resonate [14]. Bond lengths and angles in the molecule agree with generally expected values. Also, the other variations are since the computational results belong to molecules in gaseous phase and that experimental findings belong to solid state.

4.2 Vibrational analysis

The vibrational spectrum is mainly determined by the modes of the free molecule observed at high wave numbers, together with the lattice (translational and vibrational) . modes in the low frequency region. In the present work, the frequency calculation analysis is performed to obtain the spectroscopic signature of Telmisartan. Telmisartan is a 69-atom molecule. It belongs to C_1 symmetry having only identity operation. A molecule of n atoms has $3n$ degrees of freedom. Six mode of them is for translation and rotational modes [15,16].

Hence, $201(3n-6)$ vibrational modes are observed in the molecule. The vibrational assignments are calculated by and B3LYP method with 6-31G(d,p) and 6-311G(d,p) as basis sets. The observed FT-Raman and FTIR bands with their simulated wave numbers and vibrational assignments are shown in the **Table 2**. To understand the observed spectral features, comparison of the observed and simulated FTIR and FT-Raman spectra of Telmisartan are depicted in the **Fig 2 & 3**.

C-H Vibrations

The C-H stretching vibrations of heterocyclic aromatic compound and its derivatives generally occur in the region from $3000-3100\text{cm}^{-1}$ [17,18,19]. Hence in the present study, the C-H vibrations observed at 3028 , 3047 , 3055 , 3070 and 3103cm^{-1} by B3LYP/6-31 G(d,p) method and those at 2991 , 3020 , 3035 , 3050 and 3072cm^{-1} were identified as C-H stretching vibrations. The C-H bending vibrations were found to be well within the characteristic region [15, 16].

Fig 2: Experimental and Theoretical FTIR and FT-Raman Spectra of Telmisartan

C-C vibrations

Generally, the C-C stretching vibrations of aromatic compounds exhibit their characteristic region 1430 to 1650cm^{-1} [20,21]. However, the actual positions are determined by the substitution around the aromatic ring.

In the present work, the experimental FT-Raman band observed at 1591cm^{-1} and FTIR bands observed at 1593cm^{-1} and that calculated at 1574cm^{-1} by B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) and 1599cm^{-1} by B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) were assigned as C-C stretching vibrations.

C-N Vibrations

The FTIR band calculated at 1249cm^{-1} and 1245cm^{-1} by both methods are attributed as C-N stretching vibrations [22]. The absorption of this band occurs at slightly higher frequency because of the increase in the force constant of C-N bond which is increased by the resonance by resonance with the ring.

O-H vibrations

The non-hydrogen bonded or free hydroxyl group of alcohols and phenols absorbs strongly in the region from 3700 - 3584cm^{-1} [22]. The O-H group vibrations are liable to be the most sensitive to the environment. Thus, they show prominent shifts in the spectra of hydrogen bonded species.

In the entitled molecule, the bands observed at 3751cm^{-1} by B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) method and that of 3803cm^{-1} by B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) method are designated as O-H stretching vibrations. These are in harmony with experimental wave numbers.

Table 2: Literature values and Theoretical optimized geometric parameters of Telmisartan by B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) and B3LYP/6-311G(d,p)

FTIR	FT-Raman	B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) method		B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) method		Assignment
		Frequency (cm ⁻¹)	IR intensity	Frequency (cm ⁻¹)	IR intensity	
3711	3713.15	3751.45	57.36	3803.41	40.08	v OH
3348.00		3223.60	7.46	3223.57	0.69	v CH
-	3204.00	3206.76	8.05	3192.89	7.44	v CH
-	3086.00	3094.62	13.90	3064.94	7.15	v CH
-	3062.80	3070.00	51.49	3050.61	14.40	v CH
-	3057.45	3055.63	11.43	3035.63	18.16	v CH
-	3051.00	3051.46	19.51	3030.53	30.56	v CH
-	-	3047.74	34.17	3025.32	38.17	v CH
-	-	3047.12	23.44	3020.56	16.61	v CH
-	-	3038.91	40.50	3018.38	37.08	v CH
2981.00	2999.59	3028.78	28.28	2991.36	19.89	v CH
1885.00	-	1811.17	311.24	1839.73	241.40	v OC
-	1636.00	1636.67	0.21	1623.13	0.14	δ CNC + δ CCN + δ
-	1612.00	1612.64	3.87	1599.27	5.36	v CC
1593.00	1591.00	1574.09	70.76	1563.62	87.38	v NC + v CC
-	1524.00	1521.73	17.60	1512.38	36.64	v CC + δ HCC + δ
-	1520.00	1520.78	16.80	1511.36	0.59	δ HCC
1513.00	-	1515.49	16.97	1504.78	28.56	δ HCH
1461.00	-	1476.06	30.28	1466.23	43.82	δ HCC + δ HCH
-	-	1459.01	83.14	1450.69	101.89	v CC + δ HCC
-	1449.00	1451.40	21.83	1439.87	24.96	v CC + δ HCC
-	-	1439.13	10.41	1431.00	35.91	δ HCH
-	1433.00	1430.82	15.14	1417.17	3.76	δ HCH
1421.00	-	1425.13	20.03	1416.75	10.62	δ HCH
1244.00	1244.00	1249.63	10.04			v CN

ν – Stretching, δ – In plane bending, β – Out of plane bending, τ – Torsion

4.3 Other Molecular Properties

4.3.1 HOMO and LUMO Analysis

A powerful practical model for describing chemical reactivity is the Frontier Molecular Orbital (FMO) theory. An important aspect of theory is the focus on the highest occupied and lowest unoccupied molecular orbitals (HOMO and LUMO). Localization of Homo orbital is very important as the electrons from this sorbital are most available to participate in a reaction. Similarly, this study predicts that a site where the lowest occupied orbital localized is a good electrophilic site.

Fig 4 : 3D plots of Homo and Lumo of Telmisartan

The shape of molecule is determined by the electron density of the molecule and this electron density depends on atomic composition of the molecule [23].

Table 1: Homo-Lumo Energy gap and related molecular properties of Telmisartan

Molecular properties	B3LYP/6-31G(d,p)
E_{HOMO} eV	-0.20624
E_{LUMO} eV	-0.05617
Energy gap	-0.15007
Ionisation potential (I)	0.20624
Electron affinity (A)	0.05617
Global Hardness (η)	-0.131205
Chemical Potential (μ)	-0.131205
Global electrophilicity (ω)	-0.0656025

The HOMO lying at the energy -0.20624a.u is entirely confined at the rings R₃, R₄, R₅ and R₆. In the same way, the rings R₁ and R₂ are entirely delocalized. The LUMO lying at the energy -0.05617 is entirely confined at the rings R₁ and R₂ and partially over the rings R₃ and R₆. The

electro density contour of the HOMO and LUMO orbitals are shown in **Fig 4**. The HOMO is molecular orbital 136 and the LUMO is molecular orbital 137.

CONCLUSION

In this study, the spectroscopic properties of Telmisartan were investigated by FTIR and FT-Raman techniques. Quantum chemical calculations such as B3LYP method with 6-31G(d,p) and 6-311G(d,p) as basis sets help us to confirm the structural properties of the entitled molecule. The comparative result of experimental and theoretical study gave as a complete description of the geometry and vibrational properties of title molecule. The HOMO-LUMO analysis of the molecule was investigated for identification of the titled molecule. In conclusion, all the acquired data not only show the method to the characterization of the molecule and may stated to ascertain the potent of the molecule.

References

- 1) Roughley, S. D.; Jordan, A. M. (2011). "The Medicinal Chemist's Toolbox: An Analysis of Reactions Used in the Pursuit of Drug Candidates". *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*. 54 (10): 3451–79. doi:10.1021/jm200187y. PMID 21504168.
- 2) Benson S.C., Pershadsingh H., Ho C., Chittiboyina A., Desai P., Pravenec M., Qi N., Wang J., Avery M. and Kurtz T. W., (2004). "Identification of Telmisartan as a Unique Angiotensin II Receptor Antagonist with Selective PPAR -Modulating Activity" *Hypertension*, Vol 43 (5), pp 993–1002.
- 3) Biberach an der Riss, Boehringer Ingelheim Pharma K.G. and Biberach, Germany (2000) "Pharmacokinetics of orally and intravenously administered telmisartan in healthy young and elderly volunteers and in hypertensive patients", *Journal of International Medical Research*, Vol 28, pp 149-167.
- 4) Philippe Gosse (2006) "A Review of Telmisartan in the Treatment of Hypertension: Blood Pressure Control in the Early Morning Hours", *Vasc Health Risk Manag.*, Vol 2(3), pp 195-201.
- 5) W. Kohn, A. D. Becke, and R. G. Parr Density Functional Theory of Electronic Structure *The Journal of Physical Chemistry* 1996 100 (31), 12974-12980 DOI: 10.1021/jp9606691
- 6) Sulpizi M, Folkers G, Rothlisberger U, Carloni P, Scapozza L (2002) Applications of density functional theory-based methods in medicinal chemistry. *Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationships* 21(2):173-181.
- 7) Hohenberg P, Kohn W (1964) Inhomogeneous electron gas. *Physical Review B* 136(3B): B864-B871.
- 8) Kohn. W, Becke. A. D, and Parr. R.G (1996) "Density Functional Theory of Electronic Structure", *The journal of Physical Chemistry*, Vo100(31),pp12974-12980

- 9) Zhurko G.A., Zhurko D.A., (2004) Chemcraft Program, Academic version 1.5 (2004). Available at <http://www.chemcraftprog.com>
- 10) Frisch M. J., Trucks G. W., Schlegel, H. B., Scuseria G. E., Robb M. A., Cheeseman J. R., Montgomery Jr. J. A., Vreven T., Kudin K. N., Burant J. C., Millam J. M., Iyengar S. S., Tomasi J., Barone V., Mennucci B., Cossi M., Scalmani G., Rega N., Petersson G. A., Nakatsuji H., Hada M., Ehara M., Toyota K., Fukuda R., Hasegawa J., Ishida M., Nakajima T., Honda Y., Kitao O., Nakai H., Klene M., Li X., Knox J. E., Hratchian H. P., Cross J. B., Bakken V., Adamo C., Jaramillo J., Gomperts R., Stratmann R. E., Yazyev O., Austin A. J., Cammi R., Pomelli C., Ochterski J. W., Ayala P. Y., Morokuma K., Voth G. A., Salvador P., Dannenberg J. J., Zakrzewski V. G., Dapprich S., Daniels A. D., Strain M. C., Farkas O., Malick D. K., Rabuck A. D., Raghavachari K., Foresman J. B., Ortiz J. V., Cui Q., Baboul A. G., Clifford S., Cioslowski J., Stefanov B. B., Liu G., Liashenko A., Piskorz P., Komaromi I., Martin R. L., Fox D. J., Keith T., Al-Laham M. A., Peng C. Y., Nanayakkara A., Challacombe M., Gill P. M. W., Johnson B., Chen W., Wong M. W., Gonzalez C., and Pople J. A., (2003) Gaussian 03, Revision C. 02, Gaussian Inc., Wallingford, CT 06492.
- 11) Sutton L.E., (1956), "The interatomic bond and bond angles in molecules and ions", chemical society, London.
- 12) Weast R.C., Astle M.J. and Beyer W.H., (1988) "CRC handbook of chemistry and physics" Vol. 69. Boca Raton, FL: CRC press.
- 13) Zaho M.M. and Shi P.P., (2010) "Melaminium perchlorate monohydrate", Acta Cryst.E, Vol 66, pp O1463 – O1471.
- 14) McNaught A.D. and Wilkinson A., (1997), Compendium of chemical Terminology 2nd Edition, Blackwell Science.
- 15) Gunesekaran S, Natarajan R.K., Syamala D. and Rathikha R., (2006), "Normal coordinate analysis of urea meta nitro benzoic acid crystal", Indian Journal of Pure and Applied Physics, Vol 44, pp 315-319.
- 16) Krishnakumar V. and John Xavier R., (2005), "Scaled quantum chemical studies of the structure and vibrational spectra of 2, 4-diaminoquinazoline and 4-amino-2-methylquinoline", Journal of chemical. Physics, Vol 312, pp 227-240.
- 17) Arivazhagan M., Sampathkumar K. and Jeyavijayan S., (2010), "Density functional theory study of FTIR and FT-Raman spectra of 7-acetoxy-4-methyl coumarin" Indian Journal of Pure and Applied Physics, Vol 48, pp 716-722.
- 18) Arivazhagan M. and Krishnakumar V., (2005), "Normal Coordinate analysis of 1-chloroisoquinoline and 2-methyl-8-nitroquinoline", Indian Journal of Pure and Applied Physics, Vol 43, pp 573-578.

- 19) Jeyavijayan S. and Arivazhagan M., (2010), "Study of density functional theory and vibrational spectra of hypoxanthine", Indian Journal of Pure and Applied Physics, Vol 48, pp 869-874.
- 20) Anbarasu P. and Arivazhagan M., (2010), "Scaled quantum chemical study of structure and vibrational spectra of 5-fluro-2-hydroxyacetophenone", Indian Journal of Pure and Applied Physics, Vol 49, pp 227-233.
- 21) Socrates G., (1980), "Infrared Characteristic group frequencies", 1st Ed., New York.
- 22) Silverstein R.M. and Francis X. Webster, (2007), "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", sixth ed., Wiley India (P) Ltd. New Delhi.
- 23) Warren J. Hehre, Alan J. Shusterman and Janet E. Nelson (1998), "The Molecular Modeling Workbook for Organic Chemistry", Irvine, California: Wavefunction, Inc. pp. 61–86.